

D4.1 REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE - RECOMMENDATIONS SUMMARY SHEET

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CIRPASS 2

D4.1 Reference architecture - Recommendations Summary Sheet

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Abstract	Summary of the Architectural Recommendations from the D4.1 reference architecture document.
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CIRPASS-2 CONSORTIUM

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41	WORLDLINE France	WORLDLINE FR	France
42	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt	PTB	Germany
43	Digital Data Chain Consortium GbR	DDCC	Germany
44	ZVEI e. V.	ZVEI e.V.	Germany
45	Association of Service and Computer Dealers International	ASCDI	US
46	Open Blockchain for Asset Disposition Alliance (OBADA)	OBADA	US
47	Green Electronics Council	GEC	US
48	Textile Exchange	TextileExchange	US
49	iPoint-Systems GmbH	iPoint	Germany

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OBJECTIVE OF THIS DOCUMENT

In deliverable D4.1, the reference architecture document¹, the CIRPASS-2 project² proposes a set of 'building blocks' together with a set of architectural recommendations. Collectively, the building blocks provide the features required for a complete DPP system. Each building block is mapped to the role in the system most likely to provide the feature. The architectural recommendations are intended to ensure ecosystem-wide interoperability and are not specific to one or more roles. This document provides a summary overview of the architectural recommendations as a quick and easy way to get an overview. The architecture document contains the background and rationale for each recommendation.

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¹D4.1 Reference Architecture

²CIRPASS-2

ARCHITECTURE RECOMMENDATIONS SUMMARY LIST

The architectural recommendations are listed below. Additional background, reasoning, and rationale for each recommendation are provided in the corresponding sections of the D4.1 Reference Architecture document.

INTEROPERABILITY

- 3.1 DPP systems should use JSON-LD as the default format for the exchange of DPPs. Other formats may be supported for increased usability and interoperability.
- 3.2 Responsible parties should use predefined, extensible, open DPP templates where available to promote semantic interoperability.
- 3.3 DPP systems should adopt the standardized core APIs for DPP lifecycle management defined by prEN-18222.
- 3.4 DPP systems should adopt, or align with, commonly used open API specifications that leverage the DPP infrastructure where authoritative guidance, such as from JTC 24 and the UNTP, is not available. Doing so can support voluntary data exchange, integration with external systems, and streamlined reporting under other EU regulations.
- 3.5 A parent product's DPP should include a verifiable, persistent link to each incorporated component that has its own DPP ('sub-DPP'), rather than merely a static copy of its data. In addition to this link, an up-to-date embedding of the data may also be considered .

IDENTITY AND AUTHORIZATION

- 3.6 Organizations should use Verifiable Credentials to provide reliable and trustworthy identity in the DPP system.
- 3.7 DPP systems should use Verifiable Credentials for digitally authenticated third-party roles. These Verifiable Credentials should preferably be issued by one or more EU trusted credential issuers as 'Qualified Electronic Attestation of Attributes (QEAA)', as proposed in the eIDAS 2.0 regulation,
 - 1 A generic set of roles should be defined at the level of the EC and detailed further where necessary under the upcoming delegated legislation as per Art. 10(g) and 11(f),
 - 2 DPP systems should use role-based access control (RBAC) as the access control mechanism.
 - 3 Role issuance to non-EU value chain actors should be made possible.
- 3.8 The publicly accessible DPP data should be provided as a JSON-LD verifiable credential and each role-specific protected data set should be provided as a separate JSON-LD verifiable credential linked to the public DPP.
- 3.9 Organizations should use eIDAS 2.0 digital identity credentials for organizational identity, and trusted public authorities should issue or guarantee Qualified Electronic Attestations of Attributes for roles and other DPP-related credentials.

DPP INTEGRITY

- 3.10 DPP issuers should format both the original DPP and all authorized updates as Verifiable Credentials based on the Verifiable Credentials Data Model 2.0 and signed with JOSE proof..

- 3.11 DPP systems should treat the initial DPP record and all subsequent updates as immutable entries. Modifications should be recorded as new, separate, timestamped entries linked to the DPP's history, not by altering previous records.
- 3.12 DPP systems should generate and provide a digitally signed receipt when it stores a DPP update submitted by an authorized third party.
- 3.13 DPP systems should store cryptographic evidence of DPP data authenticity and integrity, and other DPP-related claims, with an independent trusted third party.
- 3.14 A DPP status system should allow parties to register that a DPP is incorrect or invalid.
- 3.15 DPP backup providers should store all DPP data managed by the Economic Operator, keep the backup up to date, and enforce the same access control rules.

DPP ACCESS

- 3.16 The responsible Economic Operator should operate a redirection service that maps a product's UPI from its data carrier to the current URI of its DPP data. Data carriers should resolve to an entry in this redirection service.
- 3.17 The European Commission should operate, or ensure the operation of, an independent and persistent UPI-to-URI redirection service for the DPP system.
- 3.18 Economic Operators should make generic, model-level DPP information publicly discoverable via a standardized .well-known URI endpoint on their primary website.
- 3.19 A separate data carrier should provide access to model-level DPP data outside the physical product context (e.g., online marketplaces pre-purchase, physical store displays) and indicate the expected batch- or item-level data.

DATA MANAGEMENT

- 3.20 Products for which lifecycle events, such as repairs, are expected or required must have a unique identifier for each individual product.
- 3.21 Parties requiring frequent or bulk access to DPP data (e.g., market surveillance, large repair networks, asset managers) should consider implementing local caches or repositories of relevant DPPs.
- 3.22 The responsible Economic Operator should store relevant DPP updates throughout the product life-cycle to keep the data accurate, complete, and up to date.
- 3.23 The DPP system should include a centralized repository of key DPP attributes as search keys to support the web portal.

DISPLAY

- 3.24 The European Commission should create, or commission the creation of, a universal and standardized set of recognizable symbols or icons for key mandatory DPP data points or indicators (e.g., concerning sustainability, circularity, safety).
- 3.25 The European Commission should develop, or commission the development of, standardized display templates or clear guidelines for presenting DPP information visually to end-users.